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cells. Nanomaterials (NM) can be effectively used in germination and growth. The carbon nanotubes can be used as controllers of seed germination and factory growth. The capability of NMs to access the hard coating of seeds and allow water importation is the deciding factor for increased growth and vigour. NPs made of mesoporous silica (MSNs) can ameliorate photosynthesis by interacting with chloroplasts, performing in enhanced seed germination, increased total protein, and chlorophyll content. NPs can mimic the exertion of antioxidant enzymes in the form of nano-enzymes that can scavenge from oxidative stress. Water filtration may be bettered with the use of Nanofiber membranes and the use of nano biocides, which appear promising effective. Pervious concave silica NPs (PHSNs) with validamycin (fungicide) acts as an effective transport structure of water - answerable fungicide to control numerous conditions. Nano-mixes were precious to constructions of fungicides also it might be active in contradiction of the multitudinous pests in crop. Likewise, canvas- loaded NPs were more salutary on behalf of medications of nano- fungicides. Nano silica can be effectively used as a nano fungicide. ZnONPs and MgO NPs show antifungal exertion against *Alternaria alternate*, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Mucor plumbeus*. ZnO and MgO NPs are active antibacterial agents. In post-harvest technology of fruits and vegetables, the nanotechnology approach is helpful for controlling post-harvest conditions; introducing a new invention for packaging flicks; precluding impact of feasts and unsafe shafts; perfecting packaging appearance; and helping for labelling fresh products using the multiple chips (nano biosensors). Therefore, it's prognosticated that nanotechnology will come one of the most important forces for invention in the food packaging assiduity.

BPP-259

Elasticity in tuber crops to drought

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Potatoes and cassava are two of the world's most significant food crops, ranking in the top six. They produce more water than cereals and are regarded as one of the most energy-efficient crops. When drought happened during the tuberization period, yields were lower than when drought struck during the vegetative phase. Drought sensitivity is high in both cassava and sweet potato during storage root initiation. Tuber malformation in potatoes is caused by water stress during tuber bulking. Yam is perhaps the only root/tuber species that has been documented to have high drought resistance soon after planting. Despite their scant fine root structure, cassava develops thinner and deeper roots, allowing them to access subsoil water. During drought, water-stressed cassava plants reduce carbon cost by ceasing osmolytes production. Droughts during tuber commencement and tuber bulking significantly affect sweet potato production. At a significantly lower water potential (-1.3 MPa) than potato leaves, leaves wilt permanently. Irrigation at a moisture depletion level of 60% could boost root yield by 24% when compared to non-irrigated sweet potatoes. Yams may thrive in areas where annual rainfall is as low as 500 mm, however production potential is limited. New yam plants sprout with significant vine length expansion after surviving a dry period (sometimes exceeding two meters). Potassium

supplementation can help taro function better during droughts by enhancing stomatal control and water efficiency. If these crops are cultivated during dry seasons or in places with low annual rainfall, irrigation is still required.

BPP-260

Effect of different type of mulches on growth, yield and quality of broccoli

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The experiment was conducted during winter season in randomized block design (RBD) with three replications, consisting of nine treatments, namely, T₁: black polyethylene mulch (25 µm), T₂: black polyethylene mulch (50 µm), T₃: silver and black polyethylene mulch (25 µm), T₄: silver and black polyethylene mulch (50 µm), T₅: red Polyethylene mulch (25 µm), T₆: red polyethylene mulch (50 µm), T₇: paddy straw mulch (8 t ha⁻¹), T₈: sugarcane trash 8 t ha⁻¹ and T₉: control (without mulch). The result revealed that application of the black polyethylene mulch (50 µm) recorded better values for growth characters namely, plant height at 30 DATP (22.36 cm) and at curd harvest (60.94 cm); plant spread at 30 DATP (N-S = 22.56 cm and E-W = 20.68 cm) and at curd harvest (N-S = 53.34 cm and E-W = 52.05 cm); number of leaves plant⁻¹ at 30 DATP (12.47) and at curd harvest (24.13); length of leaves at 30 DATP (16.93 cm) and at curd harvest (42.43 cm) and stalk length (18.03 cm). While, stalk diameter did not show any large distinction through mulching. Among different 9 treatments, T₂ (black polyethylene mulch: 50 µm) was found best for curd length (13.55 cm), curd diameter (15.31 cm), marketable curd weight (333.72 g), net curd weight (277 g), curd yield plot⁻¹ (6.57 kg), curd yield ha⁻¹ (12.16 t) and harvest index (38.40%). While, minimal days to first curd initiation (47.00 days) and day to 50% curd initiation (55.33 days) were mentioned underneath treatment T₄ (silver and black polyethylene mulch: 50 µm). The curd colour and vitamin-C (mg 100 g⁻¹) have been found non-significant by means of specific mulching treatments. Thus, it can be concluded that the use of black polyethylene mulch (50 µm) is more effective in terms of growth, yield and for securing higher B:C ratio in broccoli cultivation.

BPP-261

Response of media, fertilizer and chemicals application on growth of mango rootstock

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The experiment was conducted to see the response of media, fertilizer and chemical application on growth of mango root-stock during 2017-2020 at Regional Horticultural Research Station, ACHF,